

Title: Crypto-economy application for start-up

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INTRODUCTION:

We believe it is time to disrupt how entrepreneurs, their associates and partners interact altogether. Trust is the key ingredients to entrepreneurship it is required to start, to recruit to finance. Blockchain is a game changer for strat-up. Not because it is trustless has often misinterpreted but because it can play a trusted third party role without having to overpay some middle man.

AIM:

To help entrepreneurs who want to start their project by minimizing their legal costs and simplifying management.

To help incubators support entrepreneurs by offering them legal and automated key software solutions.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS:

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- Access to services requires the possession of a token. The Ether value of the Token materializes a prepayment for the services. It is necessary for the use of smart-contracts of the network. The Token is consumed by the use of services.
- Other purpose of the token:
 - Allows setting up KYC and AML (network players can use a nickname but their account is necessarily linked to a duly identified physical person (uPort de Consensus))
 - Protect yourself from the volatility of cryptos
 - AKA network effect management
 - Reinforce the protection of operations carried out on the ETH network

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RESULTS:

- Speed of implementation of standard contracts with embedded notarial properties.
- Knowing if particular legal help is required
- Simple and fun tools plus online governance of the company.

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CONCLUSIONS:

- Automate and disrupt activities and relationships between entrepreneurs, their associates and other partners.
- Software suite offering, for a fraction of the price, the peace of mind that comes with the use of a lawyer - standard contract
- Start-up governance tools (voting and distribution tools, digital registries) : The recording of transactions (whatever their nature) in the blockchain serves to demonstrate in a non-repudiable way their existence.

KEYWORDS:

Blockchain - Ethereum - Start-up services - LegalTech – Legal Smart-contract - Incubators friendly

BIOGRAPHY:

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